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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHIJITH M K bearing USN 4SU21HM001 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKASH bearing USN 4SU21HM002 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKASH SHETTY bearing USN 4SU21HM003 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALFAZ K bearing USN 4SU21HM004 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AMOGH V bearing USN 4SU21HM005 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAMIKA RAJEEVAN bearing USN 4SU21HM006 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANANTHU K bearing USN 4SU21HM007 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARJUN RANJITH M bearing USN 4SU21HM008 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASHAKIRAN G R bearing USN 4SU21HM009 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASHWEED HAMEED bearing USN 4SU21HM010 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DEEKSHAN bearing USN 4SU21HM011 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DEEPAK BHEEMAI AH C S bearing USN 4SU21HM012 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ETHAN COUTINHO bearing USN 4SU21HM013 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JOSHUA SANTAN FERNANDES bearing USN 4SU21HM014 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms KARTHIK bearing USN 4SU21HM015 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms KEN GARETH NORONHA bearing USN 4SU21HM016 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms LOYD GLAN DMELLO bearing USN 4SU21HM017 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MADHAN KUMAR bearing USN 4SU21HM018 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MANISH bearing USN 4SU21HM019 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MANISH C SHETTY bearing USN 4SU21HM020 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms METHUSH TAURO bearing USN 4SU21HM021 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MIDHUN MOHAN M J bearing USN 4SU21HM022 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED ISMAIL bearing USN 4SU21HM023 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED RUBAB bearing USN 4SU21HM024 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED SUHAIL M K bearing USN 4SU21HM025 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUKUNDA H bearing USN 4SU21HM026 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PALLAVI KOTIAN bearing USN 4SU21HM027 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PAVAN bearing USN 4SU21HM028 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PAWAN MONTEIRO bearing USN 4SU21HM029 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms POOJITH T D bearing USN 4SU21HM030 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRAMITH B bearing USN 4SU21HM031 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRANAY AMMANNAYA K bearing USN 4SU21HM032 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRASNIL J P bearing USN 4SU21HM033 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAHUL BERNIE DSA bearing USN 4SU21HM034 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANKETH B bearing USN 4SU21HM035 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAPNA bearing USN 4SU21HM036 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHASHANK bearing USN 4SU21HM037 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHREYAS S K bearing USN 4SU21HM038 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SNEHA E V bearing USN 4SU21HM039 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREERAJ K bearing USN 4SU21HM040 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUHAIR FIRDOUS bearing USN 4SU21HM041 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUJITH SHETTY M bearing USN 4SU21HM042 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUKET MANOHAR SHETTY bearing USN 4SU21HM043 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SUTHIN BABU bearing USN 4SU21HM044 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SWEEJAN bearing USN 4SU21HM045 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms TANMAI bearing USN 4SU21HM046 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms UMMAR UL ASEES bearing USN 4SU21HM047 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VIJESH SHARVIN D SOUZA bearing USN 4SU21HM048 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VIKAS DINESH DEVADIGA bearing USN 4SU21HM049 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms YABIN JOSE bearing USN 4SU21HM050 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Third Semester of the BHMCT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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